

The Hidden Curve: A Morphological Mystery of Radix Entomolaris

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Submitted 24 September 2025
 Accepted 28 October 2025
 Published xx xxx xxxx

Access this Article Online Website: www.healtalk.in	Quick Response Code
DOI	

Abstract

Radix entomolaris (RE) is an anatomical variation characterized by the presence of an additional distolingual root in mandibular molars, most commonly the first molar. This supernumerary root presents significant clinical implications in endodontic diagnosis, treatment planning, and execution. Failure to recognize and manage this anatomical variation can lead to incomplete debridement, persistent infection and eventual treatment failure. The prevalence of RE varies among different populations and ethnic groups, necessitating careful radiographic examination and where necessary, advanced imaging techniques such as cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) for accurate detection. Clinicians must be aware of the root canal configuration anomalies associated with RE and adapt access cavity design and instrumentation techniques accordingly to enhance a successful treatment outcomes. This article presents a case report of mandibular first molar with extra root that was successfully treated using appropriate access cavity, instrument and techniques.

Keywords: Radix entomolaris, mandibular molars, anatomical variation, extra root, endodontic treatment, root canal morphology.

Introduction

Radix entomolaris (RE) refers to a dental morphological variation in which an additional third root, most commonly distolingual, occurs in mandibular molars especially the mandibular first molar¹. The term "radix entomolaris" distinguishes this feature from radix paramolaris, which appears mesiobuccally². The recognition of RE is crucial in endodontics, as undetected canals may result in incomplete cleaning, shaping, and obturation, thereby compromising treatment success³.

The additional root often exhibits a small diameter, sharp curvature, and eccentric location, complicating detection on routine radiographs⁴. Failure to identify and treat RE can lead to procedural errors and poor prognosis⁵. Therefore, the use of advanced diagnostic tools such as angled radiographs and CBCT is recommended⁶.

Epidemiological data reveal significant ethnic variation in RE prevalence. Mongoloid populations such as Chinese, Eskimos, and Native Americans show prevalence rates of 5–30%⁷, while Caucasian populations report 0.2–4.2%⁸. Indian studies reveal incidence rates between 2.19–13.3%⁹. The etiology is linked to genetic and developmental factors, including disturbances in Hertwig's epithelial root sheath^{10,11}.

Classification systems by De Moor (Type I–III) and Carlsen & Alexandersen (Types A, B, C, AC) provide morphological categorization for clinical reference^{1,2}. Modern magnification, ultrasonic instrumentation, and three dimensional imaging have enhanced detection and treatment¹².

Case Report

A 32 year old female patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics with a chief complaint of severe pain in the right lower back tooth region since last three days. The pain was intermittent in nature and aggravated on taking hot food and beverages.

Examination

On clinical evaluation, it was seen that there was deep disto-occlusal caries in lower right mandibular first molar tooth. The tooth was hypersensitive to both hot and cold stimuli and was tender on percussion, although no pathologic mobility was observed.

Radiographically, revealed the presence of deep caries involving the pulp, widening of periodontal ligament space, loss of lamina

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dura and presence of an unusual root morphology (Fig. 1). Another radiographs were taken at 20° mesial and distal angulation to confirm the presence of additional root on the distolingual aspect(R.E).

Diagnosis was established as Symptomatic irreversible pulpitis irt⁽⁴⁶⁾. Non-surgical endodontic therapy was treatment planned and patient consent was obtained.

Procedures

Local anesthesia was given.Rubber dam isolation was done.(Fig.2)

The pulp chamber was accessed and two mesial canal orifices and one distal canal orifice present eccentrically towards the buccal aspect of the tooth were initially located. The shape of the access cavity was modified from triangular to a trapezoidal form and following the laws of orifice location, another orifice was located on the distolingual side (Fig-3)

DG-16 endodontic explorer was used to locate the root canal orifices and 15 # K-file (Dentsply, Switzerland) was used to establish patency of the canals. Working length was determined using apex locator (woodpecker) and reconfirmed radiographically. (Fig-4) Biomechanical preparation was done with rotary ProTaper Next (Dentsply, Switzerland) file system. During instrumentation, 5.25% sodium hypochlorite solution was used as an irrigant and 17% EDTA solution was used as final flush.

Master gutta-percha points was placed and obturation was performed using cold lateral condensation technique with AH Plus sealer (Fig. 5). Restoration of access cavity was done with composite resin (tetric-N-ceram, ivoclar vivadent) and a post-obturation radiograph was taken.(Fig-6)

Fig-3.Access cavity preparation was done in relation to 46

Fig-4.Working length determination was done(R.V.G)

Fig-5. Master Gutta-Percha cones (R.V.G)

Fig-1. Showing Pre-Operative Radiograph (R.V.G)

Fig-2. Rubber dam isolation was done.

Fig-6. Post-obturation RVG confirmed presence of an additional distolingual root

Discussion

RE can occur in first, second, and third molars, with bilateral occurrence reported in 37–67% of cases¹³. Gender and side predilection remain inconclusive. The success of endodontic treatment depends on accurate diagnosis, thorough chemo-mechanical preparation, and complete obturation.

A prevalence of <5% in Indian populations means RE is often overlooked. Etiological theories suggest genetic predisposition or developmental disturbances. At least two angled radiographs, along with careful clinical inspection, are recommended for detection of missed canal and additional root. Modified trapezoidal access cavity help in locating the canal orifice.

Identification of missed canal can be aided by the law of symmetry, dentinal map visualization, methylene blue staining and champagne bubble test. Since RE canals often have severe curvatures, initial exploration should be with small files (size 10 or less) followed by glide path creation to avoid procedural errors¹⁴.

Diagnosis & Clinical Approach

Indicators of RE include unclear root outline on radiographs, distolingual cervical convexity, and prominent distolingual lobe. Preoperative periapical radiographs with varied angulations are essential. CBCT provides superior three dimensional visualization. Magnification aids, angled probes (DG-16), and micro-openers assist in orifice location. Severe curvature necessitates flexible NiTi rotary instruments to maintain canal shape¹⁵.

Conclusion

Radix entomolaris is a clinically significant anatomical variation, particularly in mandibular first molars. Its detection and management are essential for avoiding missed canals and treatment failure. Advanced diagnostic tools, classification awareness and modified clinical approaches increase the likelihood of endodontic success.

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